

HI REPORT ANALYSIS

November 2024

Background

This analysis was commissioned by [Offshore Norge](#) to examine HI's (Havforskningsinstituttet/Institute of Marine Research) report [Identifying priorities for the protection of deep-sea species and habitats in the Nordic Seas by Legrand et al. \(2024\), ISSN:1893-4536](#). The motivation for analyzing this report stems from several key factors:

1. The report directly impacts future marine spatial planning in the Nordic Seas.
2. The report's findings and recommendations could have significant implications for marine resource management and industrial activities in the Nordic Seas, including potential restrictions on areas available for various activities.
3. Offshore Norge, as a stakeholder in marine activities, needs a thorough understanding of the scientific basis and methodological approach used in the report to evaluate its implications and provide informed input to future management decisions.
4. The analysis seeks to verify the robustness of the data, methods, and conclusions presented in the report, particularly focusing on the conservation planning approach and the various input datasets used.

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Frontpage of the PDF version of the HI Report.

Conventions and Abbreviations

In this document we refer to *Identifying priorities for the protection of deep-sea species and habitats in the Nordic Seas by Legrand et al. (2024)* as “HI Report”.

Text citations are presented in *italics*. **Bold** highlights text segments that we would like to emphasize.

Sections that reflect our own views or go beyond the topics covered in the HI Report are labeled as “Comment” and presented in blue font.

Abbreviations used in this report analysis.

AMOR	Arctic Mid-Ocean Ridge
BLM	Boundary Length Modifier
CBD	1992 UN Convention of Biological Diversity
CCZ	Clarion-Clipperton Zone
CWC	Cold-Water Corals
FPF	Feature Penalty Factor
HDAA	High Diversity or Abundance Areas Locations with four or more CWC and sponge aggregation types per 100 km ² or more than 40 observations of CWC and sponge aggregations per 100 km ²
LDAA	Low Diversity or Abundance Areas Locations with CWC and sponge aggregations that do not fulfil the HDAA criteria.
MPA	Marine Protected Area
NECS	Norwegian Extended Continental Shelf
NEOLI	No-take, Enforced, Old, Large, Isolated
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
OSPAR	OSlo and PARis Conventions
PU	Planning Unit
SMS	Seafloor Massive Sulfide

Executive Summary

The HI Report *Identifying priorities for the protection of deep-sea species and habitats in the Nordic Seas by Legrand et al. (2024)* provides a good basis for further discussions regarding the protection of the Norwegian deep-sea areas. Our analysis of the HI Report aims to evaluate the robustness of the data, methodologies, and conclusions presented, with a particular focus on the conservation planning approach. The following points could be used to enhance future iterations of Norwegian deep-sea protection efforts:

- 1. Conservation Planning Approach.** The HI Report uses Marxan software for its conservation planning approach. Typically, the Marxan approach builds on an established framework for conservation planning. However, the HI Report does not mention this foundational framework that underpins the employed approach, nor does it provide a statement about the assumed stage of the conservation planning approach. This lack of detail complicates understanding the results in light of the usual overall conservation planning framework.
- 2. Stakeholder Involvement.** The framework for conservation planning emphasizes the importance of involving relevant stakeholders as early as possible in the planning process. The HI Report appears to overlook this critical aspect, which could hinder collaborative efforts and acceptance of proposed conservation measures.
- 3. Cost Definitions.** The Marxan model operates on a cost minimization principle, incorporating costs related to protected planning units (areas), boundaries around protected areas, and penalties for unmet conservation targets. The definition of these costs varies from project to project and typically needs to be developed together with stakeholders. It is known, from other conservation planning projects, that biologically 'pure' conservation plans are often fraught with problems. The HI Report does not define the assumed costs, which are essential for understanding the feasibility and implications of the proposed conservation strategies.
- 4. Areas and Buffers.** The report utilizes a planning unit size of 100 km² based on literature related to shallow reefs. However, it is unclear whether this size is appropriate for deep-sea ecosystems. Additionally, the report advocates for substantial buffer zones around marine protected areas to mitigate potential impacts such as waste plume spreading from activities like mining. The values proposed for these buffers are at the high end of published scientific literature, while numerous studies suggest lower values may be more applicable. Plume spreading depends on location-specific parameters such as flow, bathymetry, and geology, as well as chosen engineering solutions; therefore, site-specific evaluations are necessary. Introducing large buffers around modelled marine protection areas comes with substantial additional "area cost," which does not seem to be considered in the Marxan models presented in the HI Report.

- 5. Transparency.** While the HI Report provides a reasonable account of data sources utilized, it lacks transparency regarding specific decisions made about data selection and usage. For instance, instances where only parts of data sources (either data layers or spatial restrictions) were employed are not clearly detailed. Also, it is difficult to locate exact data sources when they are simply stated as e.g., MAREANO without further specification or direct links. There also appear to be inconsistencies between figures in the report; for example, there is apparently no underlying sponge or coral data near the Atlantic Mid-Ocean Ridge, yet when the data is cast into 100 km² hexagonal tiles, there suddenly appears to be data at a location likely corresponding to Schulz Bank. Providing exact data sources for all considered features or providing them in GIS-ready format would be valuable. Furthermore, since Marxan is open-source software used in the HI Report, making the entire Marxan project available would increase transparency and allow stakeholders to investigate proposed scenarios' details and study alternatives.
- 6. Biological Data.** The biological datasets referenced in the HI Report primarily originate from MAREANO. Since the report explicitly states that "All publicly available scientific data were collected for the area of interest," one would hope that more comprehensive data would be considered and all available scientific literature reviewed. Instead, the HI Report relies on geographical and geological data as proxies for lacking biological data across most of the study area. In this sense, three biological datasets contrast with 30 non-biogenic habitat features used as proxies.
- 7. Protection Approach.** It is unclear why some features such as inactive hydrothermal vent sites are considered priority areas requiring 100% protection while e.g., the Schulz Bank – the location with the best documented, rich benthic life near the Atlantic Mid-Ocean Ridge – is not considered a priority area. Similarly, the bulk of Norwegian sponge and cold-water coral areas are located outside the study area and are under significant human pressure (e.g., fisheries) but not well protected. The HI Report essentially argues for 100% protection of all sponge and cold-water coral areas within the study area but makes no reference to neighboring areas. A more holistic approach considering all available biological, geological, and human pressure data across Nordic Seas would make more sense.
- 8. Main Questions.** The main questions asked by Norwegian Environment Agency in their order of commissioning this report were: 1) Is it more important to protect rare species and habitats or functionally important ecosystems? 2) Do some species or habitats need greater protection than others? The HI Report does not adequately or conclusively answer these critical inquiries – particularly the first one.

Our analysis underscores the need for clearer methodologies, stakeholder involvement, and comprehensive data integration to improve marine conservation efforts in Nordic Seas effectively.

CONSERVATION PLANNING APPROACH

An overview of the selected conservation planning approach, its background, and results.

Marxan

The HI Report uses Marxan, which is the most widely used decision-support software for conservation planning globally. Marxan is free software and the underlying principles are well documented.

Marxan uses simulated annealing to minimize the objective function, which in simplified terms is the Marxan Score:

$$\sum_{PUS} \text{Cost} + BLM \sum_{PUS} \text{Boundary} + \sum_{\substack{Con \\ Value}} FPF \times \text{Penalty} = \text{Marxan Score} \quad (5)$$

The score is the sum of the three terms in the simplified function:

1. the sum of the costs of the selected planning units
2. the total perimeter of the selected planning units
3. the total penalty incurred if conservation targets are not met

Screenshot of the Marxan webpage.

Marxan is based on Ball, I.R., H.P. Possingham, and M. Watts. 2009. Marxan and relatives: Software for spatial conservation prioritisation. Chapter 14: Pages 185-195 in Spatial conservation prioritisation: Quantitative methods and computational tools. Eds Moilanen, A., K.A. Wilson, and H.P. Possingham. Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK.

Marxan Score - Example

Let us consider the simple example to the right.

We want to protect all three species and our domain consists of 3x3 planning units (PU). The conservation target is to protect one occurrence of each species.

All PUs have the same cost (PU cost = 1) and each PU boundary has a boundary cost of 1. The boundary length modifier (BLM) is set to 1, while the feature penalty factor (FPF) value for missing targets is 10.

The Marxan Score for the three solutions can be calculated by summing the cost of protected PUs, the cost of the outer boundaries of the protected areas, and the number of species that are left unprotected. Solution 1 and 3 meet all conservation targets, while Solution 2 does not (only two of three species are included in reserves).

Hence, **Solution 3** is the best solution as all conservation targets are met and the cost (Marxan Score) is lowest.

Solution 1

PU Cost = 3

Boundary Cost = 8

Penalty = 0

Marxan Score = 11

Solution 2

PU Cost = 2

Boundary Cost = 6

Penalty = 10

Marxan Score = 18

Solution 3

PU Cost = 2

Boundary Cost = 6

Penalty = 0

Marxan Score = 8

*The example material on this page is taken from
"User Manual MARXAN, Marxan version 2.43 & above"*

Marxan Score – Comment

As stated, the Marxan Score is calculated based on the cost of PUs, the cost of boundaries and the penalty for failing to meet conservation targets.

While these elements are crucial, the HI Report does not explicitly define them, which is problematic. To illustrate this, we present a simplified scenario targeting 10% protection of a single feature / habitat that happens to cover the entire study area.

Mirroring the HI Report, we set each PU to 100 km². Figure A displays Marxan's output without boundary costs. Purple hexagons represent the best solution, while the underlying grey-yellow-red colours indicate selection frequency across 10 Marxan iterations.

Figures B through D demonstrate the effect of incrementally increasing boundary costs. This progression clearly shows how the purple areas become more clustered, resulting in a more compact design with reduced boundary length. This visualization effectively illustrates how adjusting parameters can significantly influence Marxan's conservation planning outcomes, balancing protection goals with spatial efficiency.

The experiment displayed on the right focuses solely on the competing effects of the costs associated with PUs and boundaries. However, in more realistic scenarios, it is essential to also consider the implications of failing to protect species and habitats. This consideration inherently requires that we have a comprehensive understanding of the species and habitats involved.

Simplified Marxan model made by Bergwerk for the study area.

Cost – Comment

The concept of “cost” is indeed crucial to Marxan's conservation planning process. The “cost” in Marxan can represent various factors and the choice of cost metric can significantly influence the outcome of Marxan analyses. Therefore, careful consideration should be given to selecting appropriate cost data that reflects the specific context and objectives of the conservation planning project. Below we reproduce the content of Box 6.3 in the *Marxan Good Practices Handbook* where different “costs” are defined.

Box 6.3: Defining conservation “costs” in Marxan

Conservation costs are often considered secondary to biological factors in the designs of protected areas (Scholz et al. 2004), and tend to be analysed post hoc for areas selected based only on biophysical data (Stewart and Possingham 2005). Implicit in Marxan is a cost minimisation objective (see Chapter 1: Introduction) that allows users to consider costs a priori. We review three different definitions of “cost” that have been implemented in Marxan to identify a system of priority areas.

1. Cost equals area

Many conservation planning assessments define the cost as the area of the planning to identify areas that represent biodiversity targets within the smallest possible area of land or sea. In this case, the spatial variation in the cost of different conservation actions is ignored and may not lead to the identification of the most cost-effective areas for investment (Stewart and Possingham 2005, Carwardine et al. 2006, Klein et al. 2008).

2. Cost equals foregone fishing effort

The establishment of marine protected areas is often viewed as a conflict between conservation and fishing. In order to minimise this conflict, Marxan can be utilised to identify protected areas that minimise the impact of marine protected areas on fishermen, while achieving biodiversity conservation goals. For example, Stewart and Possingham (2005) used effort data for the commercial rock lobster fishery to reduce foregone fishing effort in a system of marine reserves in South Australia. Similarly, Klein et al. (2008) compiled effort data on 24 commercial and recreational fisheries to minimise the impact of marine protected areas on fishermen in central California.

3. Cost equals cost of conservation action (e.g., acquisition and stewardship)

In Australia, there are two conservation actions, acquisition and stewardship, under consideration by the national government to protect biodiversity. Carwardine et al. (2006) prioritised areas to meet biodiversity targets whilst minimising the costs of two alternative conservation actions: land acquisition and stewardship. Unimproved land value data was used to represent acquisition costs and agricultural profitability data was used to estimate the opportunity costs of landowners entering into stewardship agreements. This study found remarkable gains in financial efficiency when employing spatially variable data that reflects the cost of the planned conservation action.

Cost – Comment cont.

In Ball et al. (2009) *Marxan and relatives: software for spatial conservation prioritisation* they showcase the rezoning of the Great Barrier Reef in Australia in 2004 by the Great Barrier Reef Marine Park Authority (GBRMPA). This rezoning represents the largest successful, and most complex, real-world application of systematic conservation planning principles.

The Great Barrier Reef is a huge area off the north-east coast of Australia. It is a multi-use marine park that before 2004 had less than 5 % of its extent in no-take (no-fishing) zones. The rezoning raised the percentage that was in no-take zones to over 33 %. The target for each feature type was 20 %, and this was met for all but a couple of feature types. The use of Marxan for this exercise was interesting for a number of ecological and technical reasons:

- *The region was divided into over 17,000 planning units where each reef, and a buffer around each reef, was a planning unit. The area between reefs was divided into hexagons of around 12 km².*
- ***The cost of each planning units was derived from a linear combination of commercial fishing interests, recreational fishing interests, indigenous interests, and interests of people who would prefer particular places to be inside the reserve system (a negative cost).***
- *The most important biodiversity feature layer was the 'bioregions'. The whole system was divided into 70 bioregional types. These bioregions were derived from extensive statistical modelling and expert analysis of ecological and biophysical data. Targets of 20 %, and higher for rare reef types, were set for each feature.*
- *Reserves were preferentially set to be bigger than 400 km² where possible and each bioregion was meant to be represented in at least three well-separated reserves of at least this size. The minimum reserve size and minimum separation facilities of Marxan were used to achieve this.*

Ball et al. (2009) further write:

*It is instructive to note that GBRMPA initially ignored social and economic information and tried to get Marxan to find a biologically 'pure' conservation plan, a plan with only biological information. This is frequently done, or aspired to, but **is fraught with problems**. First, area is usually assumed to be cost, so that the problems of economic and social considerations were ignored, and the area conserved was simply minimized while meeting all conservation targets. This failed to deliver a system that was socially and economically viable.*

Planning Unit Size

The planning unit size used in the HI Report are hexagons with 100 km² area which is based on “*The MPA units must be big enough to sustain a viable population or community. The minimum targeted size is 100 km², as described in the NEOLI framework*”. MPA stands for Marine Protected Area.

The NEOLI framework is based on Edgar, G. J. et al. *Global conservation outcomes depend on marine protected areas with five key features. Nature 506, 216–220 (2014)*. The five key features an MPA should possess: **No** take, well-**Enforced**, **Old** (more than 10 years), **Large** (bigger than 100 km²), and **Isolated** by deep water or sand.

The paper by Edgar et al. (2014) investigates “four community metrics ..., each widely considered to respond to MPA declaration:

1. total biomass of all fishes;
2. total biomass of large (.250mm length) fishes;
3. species richness of all fishes (number of species sighted per transect); and
4. species richness of large fishes.

They also estimated the total biomass of three commercially important taxa (sharks, groupers and jacks), with unexploited damselfishes providing a control group for effects evident on targeted fishery groups.

Comment

The NEOLI (No-take, Enforced, Old, Large, Isolated) approach is rooted in comprehensive studies of **fish populations in shallow reef ecosystems**. Interestingly, the research reveals that the influence of area size on species metrics is not significant, as illustrated in the figure to the right.

While a PU size of 100 km² may potentially be applicable to the HI Report study area, it's crucial to note that this requires further investigation. Additional research and analysis would be necessary to definitively establish the appropriateness of this PU size for the deep sea study area considered in the HI Report.

Figure 3 from Edgar et al (2014). Mean response ratios with 95% confidence intervals for four community metrics and low, medium and high levels of five MPA features.

MPA Conservation Percentage

In 3.1 Selection of a network in the HI Report the following is stated:

A number of different MPA network scenarios were assessed protecting 50%, 40% and 30% of the study area. The 40% and 50% scenarios were chosen following empirical evidence that 40-50% protection is the minimum coverage needed to fully protect the range of biodiversity and threatened species within a given area. The 30% protection scenarios were assessed as, in ratifying the COP15 Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, Norway has committed to ecologically-coherent conservation of 30% of its ocean area by 2030 which will serve to mitigate further biodiversity loss in alignment with CBD objectives. Note: CBD stands for the 1992 UN Convention of Biological Diversity.

In Table 1 they elaborate on the details of the “Main criteria used to establish a representative MPA network for deep-sea areas of the NECS”. Under Representativity they write: 30 to 50% protection is given to all features and areas not classified as Priority areas for protection (biogeographic provinces, geomorphic features, marine landscapes, seamounts, knolls, CWC and sponges not part of the HDAAs).

Using the 30% scenario as an example, this requirement stipulates that a **minimum of 30% of each selected feature must be protected**. This includes biogeographic provinces, geomorphic features, marine landscapes, seamounts, knolls, CWC and sponges not part of the HDAAs.

Note: HDAA stands for High Diversity or Abundance Areas, i.e., areas where the are so many sponges and corals or such a diversity of them that they are added to the priority areas.

Furthermore, **The MPA network must protect 100% of identified priority areas, including hydrothermal vents, cold seeps, HDAAs of CWC and sponge aggregations and species assessed as vulnerable on the Norwegian Red List of Species.**

Network properties and components	Conservation targets for the MPA network
Priority areas for protection	<p>The MPA network must protect 100% of identified priority areas, including hydrothermal vents, cold seeps, HDAAs of CWC and sponge aggregations and species assessed as vulnerable on the Norwegian Red List of Species.</p> <p>Priority areas for protection are selected according to their:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • uniqueness or rarity, • special importance for life-history stages of species, • importance for threatened, endangered or declining species and/or habitats, • vulnerability, fragility, sensitivity or slow recovery, • structural complexity, • biological productivity, • biological diversity
Representativity	<p>The MPA network must consider the full range of features that occur in the study area.</p> <p>30 to 50% protection is given to all features and areas not classified as <i>Priority areas for protection</i> (biogeographic provinces, geomorphic features, marine landscapes, seamounts, knolls, CWC and sponges not part of the HDAAs).</p> <p>MPA units must be broadly distributed across the study area.</p>
Replication	<p>The MPA network must ensure that more than one example of each feature is protected to safeguard against unexpected, localized catastrophes.</p>
Connectivity	<p>The MPA network must ensure the exchange of individuals and genes between ecosystems and across the whole network.</p>
Adequacy & viability	<p>The MPA network must protect 30 to 50% of the study area.</p> <p>MPA units must be big enough to sustain a viable population or community. The minimum targeted size is 100 km², as described in the NEOLI framework⁴⁶.</p> <p>The selection and protection of features should conform to scientific literature.</p> <p>All MPA units must possess a buffer zone in their vicinity to protect core areas from indirect effects from human activities.</p>

Table 1, HI Report.

MPA Conservation Percentage cont.

The HI Report presents MPA conservation scenarios in figures 3 and 4 (see below), exploring conservation percentages of 30%, 40%, and 50%.

While most modelled marine protected areas are characterized by large, continuous spatial configurations, the analysis also reveals the presence of some small, single PU MPAs.

Comment

The considerable size of individual Marine Protected Area (MPA) units suggests that the underlying model may incorporate a boundary length cost function. This approach typically favors larger, more contiguous protected areas to minimize edge effects and management complexities. However, the presence of discrete, single hexagonal protection zones centered on vents or seeps across all MPA models introduces ambiguity. It remains unclear whether boundary cost was a significant factor in the design process or not.

Figure 4 of the HI Report.
Selection of three different MPA networks protecting 30% of the total study area: A (left): 30%A; B (middle): 30%B and C (right): 30%C.

Figure 3 of the HI Report.
Selection of two different scenarios of MPA networks protecting A (left): 50% and B (right): 40% of the total study area.

MPA Conservation Percentage cont.

The results showing the protection levels for each feature across various scenarios are presented in Table 2 of the HI Report, reproduced below. All priority features (highlighted in bold) achieve the required 100% protection. Orange fields indicate where Marxan fails to meet the required protection percentage for a feature. These instances only occur for biogeographic zones.

Blue colors signify that protection targets are met or slightly exceeded. Green colors indicate that protection targets are substantially surpassed, which is the case for almost all biogenic habitats. This overprotection likely occurs due to the relative proximity of normal CWC and sponge habitats to their respective High Density Aggregation Areas (HDAAs). Similarly, the "Norwegian Coast: West Norway" biogeographic zone is overprotected, again likely due to its spatial coincidence with numerous HDAAs (as illustrated in the following slides).

In section 3.3.1 in the HI Report the following statement is made regarding the protection of CWC and sponge aggregations: *In the 30%C scenario, all CWC and sponge aggregations encompassed within HDAAs were included in the MPA network. Additionally, the MPA network and its 10 km buffer zone comprise 92% of CWC and sponge aggregations not classified as HDAAs, with the remaining 8% of these located outside of the MPA network. Though excluded from the network by the model, we argue that these aggregations are nonetheless ecologically important and recommend that no activity that could result in their total or partial destruction should be permitted near their location. The management approach will require in-depth investigations conducted on a case-by-case basis to evaluate the potential risks of impact from deep-sea industries on CWC and sponge aggregations.*

Comment

This means that HI would like to protect 100% of all CWC and sponge aggregations.

Classification	Feature name	Percentage protected per scenario (within core MPA units)				
		50%	40%	30%A	30%B	30%C
Area of interest	NECS	54	43	38	41	33
	Abyss	54	42	37	40	32
	Slope	56	47	45	52	39
Biogeographic zones	Arctic biogeographic region >1000m	54	41	36	40	32
	Norwegian Coast: West Norway	36	84	82	70	75
	Barents Sea	38	21	35	42	18
	S-E Greenland-N. Iceland Shelf	55	83	26	33	25
	High Arctic Maritime	52	31	35	45	43
Biogenic habitats	CWC and sponge HDAAs	100	100	100	100	100
	CWC and sponge LDAAs	90	84	87	90	87
	Deep arctic sponge aggregation	97	50	74	91	94
	Hard-bottom sponge garden	90	88	89	93	90
	Soft-bottom sponge garden	89	88	87	83	88
	Deep-sea sea pen communities	95	88	88	93	87
	Sublittoral sea pen communities	95	93	93	89	91
	Hard-bottom coral garden	99	100	99	100	100
	Soft-bottom coral garden	100	51	75	100	75
	Cold-water coral reefs	99	99	99	99	99
	Nephtheidae meadow	87	78	84	89	81
	Vulnerable species on the Norwegian Red List of Species (<i>Sclerolinum contortum</i>)	100	100	100	100	100

Classification	Feature name	Percentage protected per scenario (within core MPA units)				
		50%	40%	30%	31%	31%
Geomorphic features	Basins	59	59	42	43	38
	Submarine canyons	62	47	40	42	34
	Escarpments	75	40	30	65	54
	Fans	59	54	37	51	31
	Plateaus	54	55	41	30	38
	Ridges	74	58	60	74	30
	Rift valleys	66	43	41	37	34
	Rises	67	41	50	67	57
	Sills	70	61	48	54	31
	Mid-ocean spreading ridges	62	52	50	63	30
	Terraces on the continental slope	86	63	30	82	33
	Troughs	58	42	43	51	39
	Smooth continental slope	83	71	34	61	33
	Marine canyons	50	40	31	30	30
	Deep sea plain	61	54	54	61	30
Continental slope plain	76	83	30	36	32	
Continental shelf plain	60	46	42	46	30	
Marine mountain landscape	62	52	55	32	37	
Seamounts	57	48	39	49	30	
Knolls	100	100	100	100	100	
Hydrothermal vents	100	100	100	100	100	
Cold seeps	100	100	100	100	100	

Table 2, HI Report.

MPA Superposition & Priority Areas – Comment

To enhance our understanding of the MPA models used in the HI Report, we superimpose them to examine their relationship with priority features. It's important to remember that the MPA network is required to protect 100% of identified priority areas. These include hydrothermal vents, cold seeps, HDAAs, and species listed as vulnerable on the Norwegian Red List of Species.

We have digitized the MPA areas across five figures from the HI Report, each representing different scenarios: 50% protection (Figure 3a), 40% protection (Figure 3b), and 30% protection (Figures 4a, 4b, and 4c). By overlaying these polygons, we can use color-coding to indicate how frequently each area is included in the MPA scenarios. Areas that are consistently included across all scenarios are considered high-priority and appear in every model.

The left figure shows all intersection areas color-coded according to their frequency of inclusion in MPA scenarios. The right figure highlights the areas designated as MPAs in all five scenarios.

In the subsequent slides, we compare these consistently designated MPA areas with features identified as high priorities.

MPA Superposition & Priority Areas – Comment cont.

Here we compare the areas included in the MPAs across all five models considered with the high abundance areas in the HI Report. These are locations with more than 40 observations of CWC and sponge aggregations per 100 km².

MPA Superposition & Priority Areas – Comment cont.

Here we compare the areas included in the MPAs across all five models considered with the high diversity areas in the HI Report. These are locations containing four or more CWC and sponge aggregation types per 100 km².

MPA Superposition & Priority Areas – Comment cont.

Here we compare the areas included in the MPAs across all five models considered in the HI Report with the distribution of hydrothermal vents and cold seeps.

The hydrothermal vents are: (1) Seven Sisters vent field, (2) Jan Mayen vent field (Soria Moria, Troll Wall and Perle and Bruse vents), (3) Ægir's vent field, (4) Copper Hill, (5) Fåvne Vent Field, (6) Mohn's Treasure, (7) Loki's Castle vent field. Cold seeps: (8) Håkon Mosby Mud Volcano, (9) Nyegga / Storegga, (10) Lofoten-Vesterålen, (11) Prins Karls Forland, (12) Vestnesa Ridge.

MPA Superposition & Priority Areas – Comment cont.

Here we compare the areas included in the MPAs across all five models considered in the HI Report with the distribution of *Sclerolinum contortum*, the sole red-listed species included in the report.

MPA Buffer Zones

The HI Report proposes buffer zones of 1 km, 5 km, 10 km and 20 km around the MPAs “based on the expected degree of impact from sediment plumes generated by deep-sea industries”.

“Existing literature suggests that a 1 km buffer zone may be insufficient to adequately shield MPA core units from sediment plumes generated by deep-sea industries.^{60,61}”

“In light of these considerations, buffer zones between 5-10 km may represent an optimal alternative for mitigating most of the sedimentation risk without significantly increasing the size of MPA units. Pending further investigations into the behavior of sediment plumes generated by deep-sea industries and their impact on marine ecosystems, the implementation of a 10 km buffer zone around each MPA unit is recommended as a precautionary measure.”

The two references cited in the HI Report are:

60. Gwyther, D. Environmental impact statement. Solwara 1 project. Nautilus Minerals Niugini Limited, Executive summary Coffey Natural Systems, Brisbane. 50 (2008).

Page 32: “Disposal of Unconsolidated Sediment and Competent Waste Material” ... “Plumes will rapidly settle on the seafloor **no further than 1 km from the point of discharge** around Solwara 1. The resultant footprint depth will be between 0.18 and 500 mm and cover an area just over **2.3 km²**. Some deposition will occur further afield, but at a thickness less than natural sedimentation rates.”

Page 33: “Plumes from Dewatering Discharge” ... “Suspended sediment will flocculate and settle on the seafloor approximately **5 to 10 km** to the west and northwest of Solwara 1. Maximum depositional thicknesses will not exceed 0.1 mm and rates of settling are less than existing deep-sea sedimentation rates as measured at Solwara 1 and South Su.”

Note: In Gwyther (2008), the discharged water is released at a depth of **25 to 50 meters above the seafloor** and contains fine suspended particles **smaller than 8 microns**.

61. Morato, T. et al. Modelling the dispersion of seafloor massive sulphide mining plumes in the Mid Atlantic Ridge around the Azores. Front. Mar. Sci. 9, 910940 (2022).

They use a 2D hydrodynamic model (MOHID) with turbulence to estimate the spread of the plume. By covering various scenarios, they observe a wide range of plume spread areas and conclude the following:

Page 14: “Although the total footprint of the different plumes varies considerably depending on the adopted thresholds and site, we can make the questionable generalisation that persistent (temporal frequency >50%, i.e., 6 months out 12 months) plumes may disperse, on average, over a linear distance of from **10 to 20 km** and cover an area from **17 to 150 km²**.”

Note: In these scenarios, the discharged water is released **30 meters above the seafloor** and contains fine suspended particles **smaller than 8 microns**.

MPA Buffer Zones – Comment

Several additional scientific publications on plume spreading have been published in recent years:

Aleynik et al. (2017)

- Area: CCZ
- Spread of suspended particles: several kilometers
- Spread of plume settlement: **6 km** normal currents, **12 km** mesoscale eddies

Jones et al. (2017)

- Area: Globally, but mainly CCZ
- Compilation of in-situ and modeling plume experiments
- Spread of plume settlement: **250 - 2000 m**

Spearman et al. (2020)

- Area: Tropic seamount
- Spread of suspended particles: 1400 m
- Spread of plume settlement: **100 m**

Munoz-Royo et al. (2022) and Peacock and Ouillon (2023)

- Area: CCZ
- Spread of suspended particles: large distances, 2 – 8 % of plume mass
- Spread of plume settlement: in the order of **10s m**, 92 – 98% of plume mass

Note: In both publications, they never refer to specific spreading distances, they only report fractions of plume mass above and below 2m elevation from the sea floor. The only estimation for plume settlement is given as O(1-10) m, to be understood as in the order of 1 to 10 meters.

Our own work, Souche et al. (under review, doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14204236)

- Area: Norwegian Sea
- Spread of suspended particles: dilution to 1 ppm within **2000 m**
- Spread of plume settlement: 90% of plume mass within **70 m**, 95% within a max. of **570 m**

Note: The plume is discharged 5 meters above the seafloor. Souche et al. estimate that 95% of the total mass fraction settles within 40 to 570 meters from the injection site. Beyond this range, particle settling becomes negligible, and the remaining material primarily remains suspended in the water column, forming a residual plume that can persist but dilutes to less than 1 ppm concentration at a maximum distance of 2 km.

General Comment

The plume spreading values cited in the HI Report are on the higher end of published scientific literature, which generally indicates shorter spreading distances.

Plume spreading depends on location-specific parameters such as flow, bathymetry, and geology, as well as the chosen engineering solutions. Discharging plume material as close as possible to the seafloor and minimizing the release of small particles can significantly mitigate the issue.

MPA Buffer Zones – Comment cont.

Our supplementary information includes a simplified scaling analysis of added area (in %) as a function of MPA aspect ratio and buffer size, presented as interactive HTML figures.

Example Results

1. Fixed Buffer Width (10 km):

We plot the added area percentage for different MPA aspect ratios against MPA area, assuming an elliptical shape. While the aspect ratio does influence the additional protected area, its effect is relatively modest. However, to limit the additional protected area to 10%, an MPA of approximately 200,000 km² is required. See red horizontal line.

2. Variable Buffer Widths:

For a fixed MPA aspect ratio of 5, we illustrate added area percentage versus MPA area for various buffer widths. The 10% limit indicates minimum MPA sizes:

- 1 km buffer: ~3,000 km² MPA
- 5 km buffer: ~70,000 km² MPA
- 10 km buffer: ~300,000 km² MPA
- 15 km buffer: ~690,000 km² MPA
- 20 km buffer: >1,000,000 km² MPA

Implications

Buffer zones significantly impact the minimum reasonable MPA size. This cost should be considered in initial analyses. Given the strong dependence on buffer width, plume spreading should be evaluated for specific regions and proposed technical approaches. For instance, waste plume release significantly above the seafloor leads to much larger spreading compared to closed systems releasing at the seafloor.

Framework for Systematic Conservation Planning – Comment

An interesting document that is referred to on the Marxan website is marxansolutions.org/a-framework-for-systematic-conservation-planning where they show the conservation planning framework developed by Pressey & Bottrill (2009). The main stages of the workflow are shown below and documented in Table 1 from their paper on the right.

Framework for systematic conservation planning as presented in Pressey and Bottrill (2009).

TABLE 1 Description of our 11 main stages of conservation planning (Fig. 1).

Stage	Description
1, Scoping & costing the planning process	Decisions are necessary on the boundaries of the planning region, the composition & required skills of the planning team, the available budget, necessary funds in addition to those available & how each step in the process will be addressed, if at all
2, Identifying & involving stakeholders	Important stakeholders include those who will influence or be affected by conservation actions arising from the planning process, or be responsible for implementing those actions. Different groups of stakeholders will need to be involved in different ways in specific stages of planning.
3, Describing the context for conservation areas	The planning team describes the social, economic & political setting for conservation planning, identifying the types of threats to natural features that can be mitigated by spatial planning & the broad constraints on, & opportunities for, conservation actions
4, Identifying conservation goals	May begin with agreement on a broad vision statement for the region that is then progressively refined into qualitative goals about biodiversity (e.g. representation, persistence), ecosystem services, livelihoods & other concerns. Goals help to identify the need for spatial data.
5, Collecting data on socio-economic variables & threats	Relevant spatially explicit data will include variables such as tenure, extractive uses, costs of conservation, & constraints & opportunities to which planners can respond. Will also involve predictions about the expansion of threatening processes.
6, Collecting data on biodiversity & other natural features	The planning team will collect spatially explicit data on biodiversity that include representation units (e.g. vegetation types), focal species & ecological processes. This may extend to ecosystem services (e.g. maintenance of water flows, carbon sequestration).
7, Setting conservation objectives	Involves interpreting goals to define quantitative conservation objectives for each spatial feature (e.g. 2,000 ha of vegetation type 16,500 individuals of each species) &, where necessary, qualitative objectives related to configuration, past disturbance & other criteria.
8, Reviewing current achievement of objectives	Remote data, & perhaps also field surveys, are used in this stage to estimate the extent to which objectives have already been achieved in areas considered to be adequately managed for conservation
9, Selecting additional conservation areas	With stakeholders, this stage requires decisions about the location & configuration of additional conservation areas that complement the existing ones in achieving objectives. Factors influencing decisions will include costs, constraints on, & opportunities for, effective conservation.
10, Applying conservation actions to selected areas	Application of conservation actions requires a variety of technical analyses & institutional arrangements to ensure that selected areas are given the most feasible & appropriate conservation management & that areas are prioritized for action when resources are limited
11, Maintaining & monitoring conservation areas	Activities ensure that individual areas are managed to promote the long-term persistence of the values for which they were established. This involves explicit management objectives & monitoring to ensure that management actions are effective.

Framework for Systematic Conservation Planning – Comment cont.

1. SCOPING AND COSTING THE PLANNING PROCESS

At the inception of the planning process the initial boundaries of the planning domain are identified, although later work for example on identifying stakeholders and collecting data on biodiversity and threats, may lead to boundaries being revised. Decisions are also necessary about the size and composition of the planning team and the funds that are available or have to be raised to address subsequent stages adequately.

2. IDENTIFYING AND INVOLVING STAKEHOLDERS

The early involvement of stakeholders, including governments, affected communities, and experts, has important benefits for the effectiveness of conservation planning. These include: eliciting information on biodiversity and planning opportunities that is not held in databases and would otherwise be unavailable; understanding the concerns and requirements of people likely to be affected and benefited by conservation actions; engendering trust and credibility among key players; engaging with people who may facilitate conservation actions financially and politically; and gaining the support of organizations and local communities responsible for implementing conservation actions and maintaining conservation areas into the future.

3. DESCRIBING THE CONTEXT FOR CONSERVATION AREAS

This stage sets the scene for all the tasks that follow. Its importance lies mainly in understanding the social, economic and cultural conditions in the planning region and how these shape constraints or opportunities for conservation. Part of this context is an understanding of which threats can be addressed spatially, through conservation actions in particular areas, and which require complementary non-spatial actions such as, for example, new local policies and regulations to facilitate environmental protection.

4. IDENTIFYING CONSERVATION GOALS

Goals are broad qualitative statements that provide a bridge between the values and beliefs upon which conservation efforts are based and the more specific, often quantitative, objectives used in systematic conservation planning. The very generality of goals can help to promote agreement among stakeholders, perhaps beginning with a vision statement for the planning region. An important purpose of goals is also to focus planning teams on the kinds of spatially explicit data that will be required (Stages 5 and 6).

5. COLLECTION DATA ON SOCIO-ECONOMIC VARIABLES AND THREATS

By this stage, context, and goals will have clarified the need for spatially explicit data on socio-economic variables that will influence decisions about specific actions and areas and potentially make conservation decisions more effective. These variables include: previous and existing conservation efforts, the costs of conservation (e.g., acquisition and management costs, opportunity costs to users of natural resources; Naidoo et al., 2006), threats to biodiversity and other natural values, and constraints on, and opportunities for, conservation action.

6. COLLECTING DATA ON BIODIVERSITY AND OTHER NATURAL FEATURES

Spatially explicit data on biodiversity have been fundamental to systematic conservation planning since its earliest application (Kirkpatrick, 1983), playing a vital, often dominant, role in shaping recommendations for investments. A characteristic of systematic conservation planning is its applicability to different kinds and amounts of data, making it relevant to virtually any terrestrial region and many marine regions. Recently, data on ecosystem services and other contributions of nature to people have become increasingly important in spatial planning.

7. SETTING CONSERVATION OBJECTIVES

A hallmark of systematic conservation planning is its use of explicit conservation objectives or targets, representing the interpretation of goals through the filter of available data. Objectives, especially quantitative ones (e.g., the extent of each representation unit or the number of occurrences of each special element), necessitate discussion about outcomes for biodiversity, limit the potential for expedient, residual conservation decisions, and encourage accountability (Margules & Pressey, 2000). Quantitative objectives allow the full potential of decision-support software to be realized (Sarkar et al., 2006). Qualitative objectives are, however, almost always needed because of our inability to assign numerical parameters to all aspects of biodiversity pattern and process (e.g., shape, connectivity, and species composition related to past extractive uses). Qualitative objectives are typically expressed as characteristics to be maximized, minimized or preferred. One of their disadvantages is that their achievement is, by definition, open to personal judgement, limiting repeatability and accountability.

8. REVIEWING CURRENT ACHIEVEMENTS OF OBJECTIVES

In few landscapes or seascapes, planners will work with a blank slate, devoid of conservation actions or previous attempts to identify priorities. In most cases there will be sufficient cultural or legal backing for existing conservation areas to lock them into the architecture of the new plan (Margules & Pressey 2000). In other cases, some established conservation areas may be regarded as preferences, not commitments (e.g., non-statutory reserves; Cowling et al., 2003). Existing conservation areas will often contribute to the achievement of objectives. A major purpose of this stage is to review this achievement of goal considering existing conservation areas, also known as Gap Analyses, before selecting new, complementary areas.

9. SELECTING ADDITIONAL CONSERVATION AREAS

Selecting additional conservation areas is what many people would associate with the term conservation planning. Three points are most relevant in this context.

Firstly, no matter how carefully and inclusively new conservation areas are identified, changes to these areas will usually be necessary before conservation actions are applied (in Stage 10). Some areas, for example, will be unexpectedly lost and some data on vegetation types and species localities will inevitably prove to be wrong.

Secondly, because many factors that determine which conservation actions are eventually applied to specific areas cannot often be predicted accurately across whole landscapes or seascapes, this stage typically identifies generic conservation areas, not spatially-explicit combinations of particular actions.

Thirdly, selection often has two aspects: analysis with decision-support systems to map the options for achieving objectives, and judgement by experts and other stakeholders to resolve these options drawing on knowledge not captured in data sets. Ideally, both aspects together will help planners balance objectives for biodiversity with the aspirations of people.

11. MAINTAINING AND MONITORING CONSERVATION AREAS

Stage 11 concerns ongoing management of conservation areas. Its main purpose is to ensure that the values for which conservation areas have been established are maintained. This requires each area to be placed in its landscape or seascape context so that its particular contributions to objectives can be identified.

Management then proceeds with a similar set of stages to the whole planning process but focused on individual areas (Margules & Pressey, 2000), with objectives identified, zoning and management activities allocated, and their effectiveness monitored, with adjustment as required.

10. APPLYING CONSERVATION AREAS TO SELECTED AREAS

Notwithstanding the increasing effectiveness of systematic conservation planning in shaping real decisions (Pressey et al., 2009; Sinclair et al. 2018), the process has often lacked continuity of information and personnel between Stage 9 and this stage (Pierce et al., 2005). There are two important consequences.

Firstly, some aspects of applying conservation actions have not had the attention they deserve. These include: managing changes to selected areas and preferred actions imposed by unexpected constraints on conservation actions, scheduling incremental conservation actions within the limits of annual budgets, and mainstreaming plans into the activities of organizations responsible for planning and development. The second consequence is that much careful and expensive planning has failed to achieve its potential outcomes.

These images and paragraphs are an illustrated version of the previous page and copied from: marxansolutions.org/a-framework-for-systematic-conservation-planning.

Framework for Systematic Conservation Planning – Comment cont.

Another version of the systematic conservation planning approach is outlined in the *Marxan Good Practices Handbook* where eight stages are described:

- 1. Identify and involve stakeholders.** *Effective conservation planning requires the involvement of stakeholders from the onset of the planning process. Engaging stakeholders encourages information exchange, enables collaborative decision-making, fosters buy-in by increasing stakeholders' understanding of decisions made, and increases the accountability of those leading the planning process. Potential stakeholders include levels of government, industry, traditional owners, land holders and concerned community members.*
- 2. Identify goals and objectives.** *The definition of clear goals and objectives for a comprehensive network distinguishes systematic conservation planning from other approaches. Conservation goals articulate priorities for the protection and restoration of biodiversity, whereas socio-economic goals seek to protect and enhance the social and economic interests of the region and the people living in it. For example, the establishment of the Great Barrier Reef Marine Park, Australia involved a balance between protecting the ecological integrity of the park while minimising the cost to industries, such as fisheries and tourism, which are dependant on the reef.*
- 3. Compile Data.** *In order to design a network that embodies these goals and objectives it is necessary to understand and map the conservation features (features to be conserved in the network). In addition, it may be useful to map human uses, threats and land tenure. Assembling the best available ecological, socio-economic and cultural data will require evaluating existing data, identifying gaps, and may involve the collection of new data to fill these gaps. Conservation features may be areas of importance to certain species, classifications that describe the different habitat types of a region, or physical proxies for the distribution of biodiversity; maps of human uses may depict places of high value for fishing, mining or forestry; threats may include highly developed areas or point sources of pollution; and tenure could include lands held in fee-simple (free-hold), licences (leasehold) and claims for resource extraction, and traditional ownership or stewardship by indigenous people.*
- 4. Establish conservation targets and design principles.** *Conservation targets specify how much of each conservation feature (such as species and habitat types) to protect within the network. Design principles exert influence over the geographic configuration of the network, addressing factors such as size, shape, number and connectivity of sites, with the goal of ensuring persistence and ecological integrity in a truly cohesive network. Conservation targets may be statements such as “protect 20% of each bioregion” or “at least 10 turtle nesting sites;” design principles may include “design a network with sites no smaller than 20 km²,” “select between 7 and 12 sites,” or “keep the edge to area ratio of the network low.”*
- 5. Review existing protected areas and identify network gaps.** *Most protected area networks do not begin with a “blank slate.” Typically, there will be existing protected areas to build on. Once features are mapped and targets set, it becomes possible to review existing protected areas to determine the extent to which they already encompass conservation features, meet conservation targets, and provide meaningful protection toward network goals. In some cases, existing protected areas can contribute to goals and targets with enhanced management.*
- 6. Select new protected areas.** *This step addresses the task of filling in the gaps identified in the previous step. Alternative designs are generated for complete network configurations, laying out options for a cohesive network that meets conservation targets and the design criteria. From the range of possible network configurations, new sites will be selected for protection. It is in this step that decision-support tools like Marxan are most helpful.*
- 7. Implement conservation action.** *The implementation of conservation measures involves decisions on fine-scale boundaries, appropriate management measures, and other site-specific considerations. In cases where all sites in the network cannot be protected at once it may be necessary to implement interim protection and set priorities for sequencing of implementation.*
- 8. Maintain and monitor the protected area network.** *Once a network is in place, the original goals and objectives will inform management and monitoring necessary to evaluate whether management is effectively preserving ecological integrity, and whether the site makes a meaningful contribution to the network.*

Framework for Systematic Conservation Planning – Comment cont.

The HI Report does not explicitly reference the systematic conservation planning framework or indicate its current stage in the process. Additionally, there is no mention of stakeholder involvement. In Chapter 4, the HI Report states that *Studies from the CCZ have demonstrated that it is vital that MPAs are established before licenses for industrial activities are granted in order to afford sufficient protection to all targeted habitat types within the study area.* This precautionary principle (føre-var-prinsippet) aligns with reasonable logic. However, it is essential to follow the entire Framework for Systematic Conservation Planning approach outlined in earlier slides.

For a transparent and effective conservation process, adhering to all the stages of systematic conservation planning is crucial. This includes identifying and involving stakeholders from the outset, which fosters collaborative decision-making and accountability, ultimately enhancing the overall effectiveness of conservation efforts.

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INPUT DATA

Input data used in the HI Report.

Appendix 1 (A1)

The most detailed description of the input data used in the HI Report can be found in the appendix. Appendix 1 provides an overview table of the all the features that are used in the Marxan model.

Comment

The layers referenced in the report are not available in GIS-ready formats, presenting a significant hurdle for analysis. Furthermore, there appear to be inconsistencies between the layer descriptions and their actual implementation in the Marxan model. Considerable effort and investigative work is required to compile and align the data to accurately represent the information presented in the HI Report. These challenges underscore the need for improved data management and transparency in the modeling process.

Classification	Layer	Definition	OSPAR status assessment for region I	Area (km ²); Occurrence	Data source
Area of interest		All the seabed of the continental slope ¹ and the abyss ² belonging to the Norwegian extended continental shelf ¹ .		1 231 981	Kartverket - Georange & Harris et al. (2014) ²
		¹ Deepening seafloor out from the shelf edge to the upper limit of the continental rise, or the point where there is a general decrease in steepness			
		² Area of seafloor located at depths below the foot of the continental slope and above the depth of the hadal zone (defined as deeper than 6000 m) ³ Outer limits of the Norwegian continental shelf and areas of the extended continental shelf extending beyond 200 nautical miles from the baselines			
Biogeographic zones	Arctic biogeographic region >1000m			1 121 266	
	Norwegian Coast: West Norway			40 751	
	Barents Sea			24 602	Dinter (2001) ⁵⁵
	S-E Greenland-N. Iceland Shelf			8 145	
	High Arctic Maritime			224 138	
Geomorphic features	Basins	Depression, in the seafloor, more or less equidimensional in plan and of variable extent		560 975	
	Submarine canyons	Steep-walled, sinuous valleys with V-shaped cross sections, axes sloping outwards as continuously as river-cut land canyons and relief comparable to even the largest of land canyons		53 402	
	Escarpments	Elongated, characteristically linear, steep slope separating horizontal or gently sloping sectors of the sea floor in non-shelf areas		53 593	
	Fans	Relatively smooth, fan-like, depositional feature normally sloping away from the outer termination of a canyon or canyon system		57 566	
	Plateaus	Flat or nearly flat elevations of considerable areal extent, dropping off abruptly on one or more sides		236 419	
	Ridges	Isolated (or group of) elongated narrow elevation(s) of varying complexity having steep sides, often separating basin features		39 581	Harris et al. (2014) ²
	Rift valleys	Elongated, local depressions flanked generally on both sides by ridges		8 755	
	Rises	Features that abut continental margins and do not include the mid-ocean ridge		300 462	
	Sills	Sea floor barrier of relatively shallow depth restricting water movement between basins		806	
	Mid-ocean spreading ridges	The linked major mid-oceanic mountain systems of global extent		72 274	
	Terraces on the continental slope	Isolated (or group of) relatively flat horizontal or gently inclined surface(s), sometimes long and narrow, which is (are) bounded by a steeper ascending slope on one side and by a steeper descending slope on the opposite side		80 100	
	Troughs	Long depression of the seafloor characteristically flat bottomed and steep sided and normally shallower than a trench		20 373	
	Smooth continental slope	Areas of continental slope between canyons and between the continental shelf break and the deep-sea plain		393 453	
	Marine canyons	Deep gorge with steep margins incised into the continental slope		3 169	
	Deep sea plain	Deep ocean floor below continental slope comprising both abyssal plain and continental rise. Relative relief is typically low (<50 m)		541 068	
	Continental slope plain	Plateau on the continental slope where the seabed has minor relief variations (relative relief <50 m) and usually a thick sediment cover		80 732	Norges Geologiske Undersøkelse (NGU) and MAREANO
	Continental shelf plain	Plain on the continental shelf forming a relatively flat (relative relief <50 m) platform between the continental slope and the strandflat/coast		4 276	
	Marine mountain landscape	Area of the seabed with relative relief >50 m within a square of 1 km ² , but without well-defined valleys		192 247	
	Hydrothermal vents	Underwater hot seeps that usually occur in tectonically active settings such as mid-ocean ridges. When seawater percolates into fissures in the ocean crust, the high-pressure and high-temperature conditions induce emissions of hot fluids rich in dissolved components such as metals and gases ⁵³	Good condition	14	InterRidge Vents database Ver. 3.4
	Cold seeps	Areas of the deep sea where hydrocarbon-rich fluids escape from cracks in the seafloor. The seawater expelled from the seafloor at cold seeps has a temperature close to the surrounding waters ⁵⁴	Not assessed	5	Åström et al. (2020) ⁶⁴
Seamounts	Isolated geological features with an elevation greater than 1000 m above the surrounding seafloor	Poor condition	253	Yesson et al. (2011) ⁶⁵	
Knolls	Isolated geological features with an elevation between 100 and 1000 m above the surrounding seafloor	Not assessed	1384	Yesson et al. (2011) ⁶⁵	
Biogenic habitats	Deep arctic sponge aggregations	Habitat formed by several species of hexactinellid sponges occurring in high densities in deep cold waters	Poor condition (OSPAR Deep-sea Sponge Aggregations)	121	
	Hard-bottom sponge gardens	Habitat formed by a range of medium- to large-sized sponges that colonize hard substrates such as bedrock, lithified crust, and rocks	Poor condition (OSPAR Deep-sea Sponge Aggregations)	988	
	Soft-bottom sponge gardens	Habitat formed by dense aggregations of a variety of large sponge species occurring on gravel and coarse-sand bottoms	Poor condition (OSPAR Deep-sea Sponge Aggregations)	675	
	Deep-sea sea pen communities	Patches of the deep-sea sea pen species <i>Umbellula</i> spp. occurring in deep waters (below 700 m)	Not assessed	202	
	Sublittoral sea pen communities	Areas of bioturbated fine sediments with relatively high densities of sea pens (<i>Funiculina quadrangularis</i> , <i>Virgularia mirabilis</i> , <i>Pennatulia phosforea</i> and <i>Xophobolemann stelliferum</i>) occurring at depths shallower than 700 m	Unknown (OSPAR Sea-pen and Burrowing Megafauna Communities)	884	Institute of Marine Research (MAREANO)
	Hard-bottom coral gardens	Habitat formed by sea fan populations colonizing hard substrate in locations with strong currents	Poor condition (OSPAR Coral Gardens)	232	
	Soft-bottom coral gardens	Dense aggregations of corals (usually gorgonians of the families <i>Isididae</i> and <i>Chrysogorgiidae</i>) on sandy mud substrates	Poor condition (OSPAR Coral Gardens)	69	
	Cold-water coral reefs	Complex structural habitats formed by scleractinian corals. <i>Desmophyllum pertusum</i> (syn: <i>Lophelia pertusa</i>) can build individual reefs or reef areas that can be composed of >100 individual reefs	Poor condition (OSPAR <i>Lophelia pertusa</i> reefs)	153	
	Nephtheidae meadows	Dense aggregations of cauliflower corals of the family Nephtheidae (<i>Duva florida</i> , <i>Dirfa glomerata</i> , and <i>Gersemia</i> sp.)	Poor condition (OSPAR Coral Gardens)	2 457	
	Siboglinidae	Family of annelid tubeworms inhabiting deep-sea reducing habitats such as anoxic mud-bottom substrates, hydrocarbon seeps and hydrothermal vents	Not assessed	33 (<i>Sclerolium consortum</i>) 3692 (other species)	Artsdatabanken

OSPAR Assessment (1/2)

The table in Appendix 1 also provides the OSPAR status assessment (for region 1, which is the OSPAR region for the study area).

Classification	Layer	Definition	OSPAR status assessment for region I	Area (km ²); Occurrence	Data source
	Hydrothermal vents	Underwater hot seeps that usually occur in tectonically active settings such as mid-ocean ridges. When seawater percolates into fissures in the ocean crust, the high-pressure and high-temperature conditions induce emissions of hot fluids rich in dissolved components such as metals and gases ⁶³	Good condition	14	InterRidge Vents database Ver. 3.4
	Cold seeps	Areas of the deep sea where hydrocarbon-rich fluids escape from cracks in the seafloor. The seawater expelled from the seafloor at cold seeps has a temperature close to the surrounding waters ⁶⁴	Not assessed	5	Åström <i>et al.</i> (2020) ⁶⁴
	Seamounts	Isolated geological features with an elevation greater than 1000 m above the surrounding seafloor	Poor condition	253	Yesson <i>et al.</i> (2011) ⁶⁵
	Knolls	Isolated geological features with an elevation between 100 and 1000 m above the surrounding seafloor	Not assessed	1384	Yesson <i>et al.</i> (2011) ⁶⁵
Biogenic habitats	Deep arctic sponge aggregations	Habitat formed by several species of hexactinellid sponges occurring in high densities in deep cold waters	Poor condition (OSPAR Deep-sea Sponge Aggregations)	121	Institute of Marine Research (MAREANO)
	Hard-bottom sponge gardens	Habitat formed by a range of medium- to large-sized sponges that colonize hard substrates such as bedrock, lithified crust, and rocks	Poor condition (OSPAR Deep-sea Sponge Aggregations)	988	
	Soft-bottom sponge gardens	Habitat formed by dense aggregations of a variety of large sponge species occurring on gravel and coarse-sand bottoms	Poor condition (OSPAR Deep-sea Sponge Aggregations)	675	
	Deep-sea sea pen communities	Patches of the deep-sea sea pen species <i>Umbellula</i> spp. occurring in deep waters (below 700 m)	Not assessed	202	
	Sublittoral sea pen communities	Areas of bioturbated fine sediments with relatively high densities of sea pens (<i>Funiculina quadrangularis</i> , <i>Virgulularia mirabilis</i> , <i>Pennatula phosforea</i> and <i>Kophobolemnon stelliferum</i>) occurring at depths shallower than 700 m	Unknown (OSPAR Sea-pen and Burrowing Megafauna Communities)	884	
	Hard-bottom coral gardens	Habitat formed by sea fan populations colonizing hard substrate in locations with strong currents	Poor condition (OSPAR Coral Gardens)	132	
	Soft-bottom coral gardens	Dense aggregations of corals (usually gorgonians of the families Isididae and Chrysogorgiidae) on sandy mud substrates	Poor condition (OSPAR Coral Gardens)	69	
	Cold-water coral reefs	Complex structural habitats formed by scleractinean corals. <i>Desmophylum pertusum</i> (syn: <i>Lophelia pertusa</i>) can build individual reefs or reef areas that can be composed of >100 individual reefs	Poor condition (OSPAR <i>Lophelia pertusa</i> reefs)	153	
	Nephtheidae meadows	Dense aggregations of cauliflower corals of the family Nephtheidae (<i>Duva florida</i> , <i>Drifa glomerata</i> , and <i>Gersemia</i> sp.)	Poor condition (OSPAR Coral Gardens)	2 457	
	Siboglinidae	Family of annelid tubeworms inhabiting deep-sea reducing habitats such as anoxic mud-bottom substrates, hydrocarbon seeps and hydrothermal vents	Not assessed	33 (<i>Sclerolinum consortium</i>) 3692 (other species)	

Appendix 1, HI Report.

OSPAR Assessment (2/2)

OSPAR is the mechanism by which 15 Governments & the EU cooperate to protect the marine environment of the North-East Atlantic.

OSPAR started in 1972 with the Oslo Convention against dumping and was broadened to cover land-based sources of marine pollution and the offshore industry by the Paris Convention of 1974. These two conventions were unified, up-dated and extended by the 1992 OSPAR Convention. The new annex on biodiversity and ecosystems was adopted in 1998 to cover non-polluting human activities that can adversely affect the sea.

The fifteen Governments are Belgium, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Iceland, Ireland, Luxembourg, The Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

OSPAR is so named because of the original Oslo and Paris Conventions ("OS" for Oslo and "PAR" for Paris).

Comment

It's striking to observe the severe impact of fishing on various habitats. Notably, in areas of potential mining interest, either these habitats are absent or data about them is lacking.

Below an example of OSPAR assessment:

Coral gardens are assessed as being in **poor overall status in Arctic Waters (Region I), Greater North Sea (Region II), Bay of Biscay and Iberian Coast (Region IV) and Wider Atlantic (Region V)** due to their **high vulnerability to impacts from fishing**, continued fishing pressure overlapping with their distribution, and slow recovery due to their biology. Knowledge on where coral gardens occur has increased considerably which facilitates future management.

Status Assessment 2022 - Coral Gardens

Coral gardens are assessed as being in poor overall status in Arctic Waters (Region I), Greater North Sea (Region II), Bay of Biscay and Iberian Coast (Region IV) and Wider Atlantic (Region V) due to their high vulnerability to impacts from fishing, continued fishing pressure overlapping with their distribution, and slow recovery due to their biology. Knowledge on where coral gardens occur has increased considerably which facilitates future management.

Assessment of status	Distribution	Extent	Condition	Previous OSPAR status assessment	Status (overall assessment)	
Region	I	↔ _{2,5}	↗ ₅	↓ _{3,5}	•	Poor
	II	↔ _{2,5}	↗ ₅	↓ ₅	•	Poor
	III				•	NA
	IV	↔ _{2,5}	↗ ₅	↓ ₅	•	Poor
	V	↔ _{2,5}	↗ ₅	↓ _{4,5}	•	Poor

Assessment of threats	Fishing, particularly demersal trawling and long lining	Climate change and ocean acidification	Threat or impact	
Region	I	↔ _{1,5}	↗ ₃	
	II	↓ _{1,5}	↗ ₃	
	III			
	IV	↔ _{1,5}	↗ ₃	
	V	↔ _{1,5}	↗ ₃	

A2 Biogeographic Region and Provinces

The biogeographic region and provinces is based on
Dinter, W. P. Biogeography of the OSPAR maritime area: a synopsis and synthesis of biogeographical distribution patterns described for the North East Atlantic.
(Federal Agency for Nature Conservation, 2001).

Unfortunately, we did not find this dataset in electronic GIS-ready form.

Appendix 2 in the HI Report.
Distribution of biogeographic Arctic region and provinces within the study area.

A3 Geomorphic Features – Harris et al. (2014)

The geomorphic features taken from Harris et al. (2014) are shown in the figure on the right. Interestingly, *Abyss* and *Slope* are not on the list of geomorphic features that they use, according to *Appendix 1*.

Other features from Harris et al. (2014) that are not used are shown in the figure below. *Glacial troughs*, *Bridges*, *Shelf*, and *Shelf Valleys* do not exist in the region of interest. *Seamounts* are mapped very coarse and the *Abyssal Classification* is probably not needed with all the other features.

Comment

The exclusion of *Abyss*, *Slope*, and *Seamounts* features lacks clear justification. Possible reasons include overlap with the NGU dataset or insufficient detail in Harris et al. (2014) mapping. The use of coarse geomorphic features as proxies for biological data is concerning.

Recommending protection based on these broad classifications risks oversimplification and potentially misguided conservation efforts.

Appendix 3 in the HI Report.
Map of the geomorphic features for the study area.

A4 Geomorphic Features – NGU Marine Landscapes

The geomorphic features taken from the NGU Marine Landscapes are shown on the right.

Several layers are not used. Some features, such as the *Coastal plain* and *Open fjord*, are entirely absent from the study area, while others, like *Marine valley* and *Shallow marine valley*, are only minimally present along the eastern border, see grey circles below.

Appendix 4 in the HI Report.
Map showing NGU Marine Landscapes for the study area. Data from the Geological Survey of Norway (NGU).

A5 Geomorphic Features – Seamounts & Knolls

The seamounts and knolls are taken from Yesson et al. (2011). They can be downloaded from *pangaea.de*. They provide the tops (peaks) of both types of features and that is what seems to be used in the HI Report and what is visualized in their figure.

The dataset also contains the base of both seamounts and knolls, but those polygons plot strangely, see below (left). If we filter by *Filter=1* then at least we get rid of multiples, see below (middle). The issue of multiples is further visualized on the plot where we show the GEBCO bathymetry in the background. **Individual knolls and seamounts are clearly listed multiple times.**

Appendix 5 in the HI Report.
Map of the distribution of seamounts and knolls in the study area.

A5 Seamounts & Knolls – Comment

The multiple listings of individual knolls and seamounts may skew the results of the Marxan planning approach. Additionally, the absence of a reliable area definition (see previous slide) hampers the identification of representative areas for knolls and seamounts, which are potentially crucial habitats for benthic life.

Knoll (blue) and seamount peaks (red) compared to GEBCO bathymetry.

A6 Hydrothermal Vents and Cold Seeps

As written in the HI Report summary the developed MPA network *protects 100% of all known active and inactive hydrothermal vents and cold seeps, as well as 100% of the areas defined as coral and sponge hotspots.*

The hydrothermal vents shown in the figure to the right are: (1) Seven Sisters vent field; (2) Jan Mayen vent field (Soria Moria, Troll Wall and Perle and Bruse vents); (3) Ægir's vent field; (4) Copper Hill; (5) Fåvne Vent Field; (6) Mohn's Treasure; (7) Loki's Castle vent field. Cold seeps: (8) Håkon Mosby Mud Volcano (9) Nyegga/Storegga (10) Lofoten-Vesterålen (11) Prins Karls Forland (12) Vestnesa Ridge.

Appendix 6 in the HI Report.
Map showing the distribution of hydrothermal vents (active, inferred and inactive) and cold seeps in the study area.

Hydrothermal Vents – Comment

An argument for why one may want to protect inactive hydrothermal vents can maybe be found in [Høring - Konsekvensutredning for mineralvirksomhet på norsk kontinentalsokkel og utkast til beslutning om åpning av område](#). There Pedersen et al. contribute report 3: *Fagutredning Mineralressurser i Norskehavet: Landskapstrekk, Naturtyper og Bentiske Økosystemer*.

Skillet mellom aktive og inaktive SMS-forekomster er imidlertid ikke alltid klart, fordi inaktive forekomster lokalisert i et hydrotermisk aktivt felt kan reaktiveres gjennom tektonisk aktivitet. Det er også verdt å merke seg at gruvedrift på en inaktiv sulfidforekomst kan endre underjordiske væskeveier, noe som potensielt kan føre til reaktivering av hydrotermisk aktivitet i utvinningsområdet og endringer i intensitet og karakteristikk for den varme utstrømningen på nærliggende aktive lokaliteter (Jamieson & Gartman, 2020). Et slikt scenario vil utgjøre en klar risiko for alvorlig skade på økosystemer ved varme kilder (Van Dover et al., 2020).

Denne rapporten følger terminologien i [Van Dover \(2019\)](#) og definerer inaktive sulfider som områder med akkumulerte sulfidmineraler uten pågående hydrotermisk aktivitet. Terminologien gjør ingen antagelser om hvorvidt hydrotermisk aktivitet kan gjenopptas, og omfatter en rekke forhold og geologiske omgivelser, fra inaktive skorsteiner innenfor aktive områder med oppstrømming til avsetninger som ikke lenger er i nærheten av aktive systemer og som kan være begravet under flere meter med sediment.

Den kilde-endemiske mikro- og makrofaunaen reduseres når hydrotermisk aktivitet avtar og er fraværende på inaktive SMS-forekomster, der den erstattes med et samfunn av bakgrunnsarter som ikke er avhengige av kjemoautotrofi for å overleve, og som også lever på andre harde substrater i regionen (gjennomgått av Boschen et al., 2013; Van Dover, 2019).

Typisk bakgrunnsfauna registrert fra inaktive sulfider er hovedsakelig filterspisere som svamper, hydroider, bambuskoraller, anemoner, sjøstjerner i orden *Brisingida*, slangestjerner og sjøliljer, men også kjøttetende svamper i familien *Cladorhizidae*, sjøpølser og trollhummer (Boschen et al., 2015; 2016; Galkin, 1997; Collins & Kennedy, 2012). Disse organismene kan forekomme ved høyere tetthet på inaktive sulfider plassert nærliggende aktive varme kilder sammenlignet med andre habitater, muligens fordi de kan drar nytte av ekstra næringstilgang bestående av partikler og/eller organismer transportert fra aktive skorsteiner (Erickson et al., 2009).

Minst to arter av albuesnegler og to arter flerbørstemark har blitt beskrevet utelukkende fra inaktive sulfider (Van Dover, 2019).

However, Van Dover (2019) also writes: *To date, there remains **no scientific case for exclusive fidelity of taxa only known from inactive sulfides** to the inactive sulfide habitat, although the putative grazers (limpets) and deposit feeders (ampharetids) might plausibly be specialist consumers of heterotrophic or autotrophic microorganisms.*

Including inactivate hydrothermal vents as priority areas may therefore be overly cautious.

**FAGUTREDNING MINERALRESSURSER I NORSKEHAVET
LANDSKAPSTREKK, NATURTYPER OG BENTISKE ØKOSYSTEMER**

SENTER FOR DYPHAVSFORSKNING
UNIVERSITETET I BERGEN

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6) NORCE

INNHOLD
Forord
Sammendrag
Del I:
Landskapstrekk og naturtyper
Del II:
Bentiske økosystemer
Appendiks I:
Bunnskart og gradientkart

A7 Cold-Water Corals

The Institute of Marine Research (MAREANO) is cited as the source for cold-water coral (CWC) data in Appendix 1 of the HI Report. This broad specification initially posed challenges in locating the corresponding dataset. However, by combining the [Sårbare marine bunndyr](#) and [Korallrev](#) layers from geonorge.no, we were able to recreate a dataset that closely resembles the one used in the HI Report.

The *Korallrev* dataset contains observations of *Lophelia pertusa* (*Desmophyllum pertusum*) reefs from several sources, including MAREANO, but also e.g., observations from fishermen and the petroleum industry. Since the dataset contains data from other sources than MAREANO it is assumed that this data differs some from what was used for the HI Report.

Our reconstructed dataset, shown to the left, displays a distribution pattern that closely aligns with the HI data presented in the figure on the right. A detailed comparison of data points in the Lofoten region confirms that our identified locations coincide with those in the HI dataset quite well, but that there are some differences (blue circle).

Another notable discrepancy between the two datasets occurs in the High Arctic region. In this area, the HI Report appears to have excluded certain data points without providing a rationale for their omission.

Appendix 7 in the HI Report.
Map showing the distribution of the stations where cold-water corals were observed in the study area. Data from the Institute of Marine Research (MAREANO).

A8 Deep Sea Sponge Aggregations

As with the CWCs, MAREANO is referenced as the source for Deep Sea Sponge Aggregation data in Appendix 1 of the HI Report. It appears that the [Sårbare marine bunndyr](#) layer from geonorge.no contains the necessary data.

Our dataset, shown in the bottom left, exhibits a distribution pattern that closely aligns with the HI data presented in the figure on the right. A thorough comparison of data points in the Lofoten region indicates that our identified points largely coincide with those in the HI dataset. The only significant discrepancy between the two datasets occurs in the High Arctic region, where the HI Report seems to have excluded certain data points without providing a clear rationale for their omission.

Appendix 8 in the HI Report.
Map showing the distribution of the stations where deep-sea sponge aggregations were observed in the study area. Data from the Institute of Marine Research (MAREANO).

CWC and Sponge Aggregations – Comment

An important aspect of the CWC and sponge data is that it concerns aggregations, meaning that observations involve groups of sponges or corals rather than individual specimens. The HI Report identifies nine different types of CWC and sponge aggregations, detailed in a table in Appendix 1 and further explained on [MAREANO's web pages](#) (except for Nephtheidae meadows). Each habitat type may include one or more indicator species. Mapping these aggregations is valuable as they highlight biological hotspots, but the **lack of a quantitative definition for an aggregation makes data comparison and evaluation challenging**.

For example, when comparing indicator species data for soft-bottom sponge aggregations from the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS, left) with data from [Sårbare marine bunndyr](#) (right), discrepancies arise. OBIS data shows observations in four distinct areas that differ from those in [Sårbare marine bunndyr](#) (white arrows), particularly for *Geodia* spp. and *Stelletta* spp.

A closer examination (below) reveals numerous observations of these species in these regions. Without a quantitative definition for aggregations, it is difficult to determine whether these areas qualify as HDAs or LDAs, complicating the integration of other datasets with MAREANO's data.

The areas marked by the yellow points on the OBIS map are areas with many observations.

CWC and Sponge Aggregations – Comment cont.

As highlighted in the previous slide, the absence of standardized quantitative definitions for aggregation habitat types poses a significant challenge when comparing and evaluating data. This issue is not specific to the HI Report but but a general issue.

[Meyer \(2022\)](#) summarizes the situation for sponge aggregations:

“While there is not a clear quantitative metric that classifies what constitutes a sponge ground based on the area or volume, studies have indicated the presence of sponge grounds are when the structure-forming sponges constitute up to 90% of non-fish biomass in trawl data (Klitgaard and Tendal, 2004), extend over at least 25 m² (OSPAR, 2008), occur every 1 to 30 m² (ICES, 2009), or have 0.5 to 1 sponge per 1 m² in video-based surveys (Hogg et al. 2010; Kutti et al., 2013). But as of yet, there is no agreed upon definition and further exploration is needed to help parameterize our understanding of what constitutes a sponge ground.”

From the background document of [OSPAR category Coral Gardens](#) (relevant for hard-bottom coral gardens, soft-bottom coral gardens and Nephtheidae meadows in the HI Report):

“The main characteristic of a coral garden is a relatively dense aggregation of colonies or individuals of one or more coral species. “

*Further: “Densities of coral species in the habitat vary depending on taxa and abiotic conditions [...]. The few scientific investigations available indicate that smaller species (e.g. the gorgonians *Acanthogorgia* and *Primnoa*, and stylasterids) can occur in higher densities, e.g. 50 – 200 colonies per 100 m², compared to larger species, such as *Paragorgia*, which may not reach densities of 1 or 2 per 100 m². Depending on biogeographic area and depth, coral gardens containing several coral species may in some places reach densities between 100 and 700 colonies per 100 m². [...] Currently, it is not possible to determine threshold values for the presence of a coral garden as knowledge of the *in situ* growth forms and densities of coral gardens (or abundance of coral by-catch in fishing gear) is very limited, due to technical or operational restrictions. Visual survey techniques will hopefully add to our knowledge in the coming years.”*

A9 Siboglinidae

In section 2.2.1 of the HI Report, it is stated that *Sclerolinum contortum*, a species of Siboglinidae worm, is prioritized for protection. However, in Appendix 1, the layer is labeled as Siboglinidae, which refers to the family that includes *Sclerolinum contortum*. The report lists 33 individuals of *Sclerolinum contortum* and 3,692 individuals of other species within the family, which can be confusing since only *Sclerolinum contortum* is red-listed. Our data shows a slightly higher count for *Sclerolinum contortum* at 38, but a lower count for other species at 537. The reason for this discrepancy is unclear, but it is not critical since the count of *Sclerolinum contortum* is approximately correct and the right locations are flagged.

Additionally, in the figure presented in Appendix 9, both *Sclerolinum contortum* and other Siboglinidae spp. are plotted using nearly identical markers. This creates further confusion, as only *Sclerolinum contortum* is red-listed.

The two small figures show our total Siboglinidae data (left) and when we filter just for *Sclerolinum contortum* (right).

Appendix 9 in the HI Report.
Map showing the distribution of Siboglinidae in the study area, based on the Artsdatabanken database.

Red listed Species – Comment

[Pedersen et al. \(2022\)](#) mention seven red listed species in the opening area that are mostly associated with hot vents and cold seeps:

- Amphipoda: *Exitomelita sigynae* (VU), *Monoculodes bousfieldi* (VU) and *Exitomelita lignicola* (NT)
- Polychaeta: *Sclerolinum contortum* (VU), *Nicomache lokii* (VU), *Paramytha schanderi* (VU) and *Pavelius smiley* (VU).

VU = vulnerable and NT = near threatened on the Norwegian red list for species from 2021.

It is not clear why HI choose to only include *S. contortum* in their assessment. However, when plotting observation data from Artsdatabanken of the other mentioned species it is evident that only *S. contortum* has observations in other areas than Ægirs kilde and Lokeslottet. These locations are already under protection in the presented MPA network design, so incorporating additional red-listed species is unlikely to change the overall outcome.

MAIN TEXT FIGURES

Figures not previously referenced.

Figure 1 Study Area

The study area used in the HI Report can be recreated through boolean operations on two polygon source layers:

- The slope polygon from Harris (2014)
- The Kontinentalsokkel from [Basisdata_0000_Norge_25833_NorgesMaritimeGrenser_GML](#)

Although this process is somewhat complex, it is effective. The logic involves:

1. Find the intersection between the slope data and Kontinentalsokkel.
2. Find the difference between Kontinentalsokkel and intersection.
3. Split the difference into separate polygons and keep the largest one.
4. Merge the intersection and largest difference polygon to create final study area.

Figure 1 of the HI Report.
Map of the study area

Figure 2 CWC & Sponge Data

Figures 2A and 2B display Cold-Water Coral (CWC) and sponge data. Both datasets are in fact habitats / aggregations. This is not evident from the figure legends, but from the caption, and is an important distinction from individual species observations. The data is gridded into 100 km² hex tiles for the purpose of the plots shown in Figure 2.

*“diversity (number of coral and sponge habitat types) and abundance (number of CWC and sponge observations) criteria were used to define **high-diversity or abundance areas (HDAAs) of CWC and sponge aggregations**. High-diversity areas were defined as locations containing **four or more CWC and sponge aggregation types per 100 km²** (Figure 2A), while **high-abundance areas are locations with more than 40 observations of CWC and sponge aggregations per 100 km²** (Figure 2B). Consequently, CWC and sponge HDAAs received full protection when designing the MPA network. CWC and sponges not included in HDAAs were considered as part of low-diversity and abundance areas (LDAAs) and were protected according to general conservation targets (30%, 40% or 50%, depending on the chosen scenario). Finally, CWC and sponges not included in the MPA network were subjected to specific conservation rules, presented below (cf. §3.3)”*

Figure 2 in the HI Report.

Maps showing:

A (left): the diversity of CWC (cold-water corals) and sponge habitat type observation per 100 km²; and
B (right): the abundance of CWC and sponge aggregation observation per 100 km² in the study area.

Figure 2 CWC & Sponge Data – Comment

Figures 2A and 2B in the HI Report depict Cold-Water Coral and sponge data at the Arctic Mid-Ocean Ridge (AMOR) using hexagonal tiles. However, this representation is inconsistent with the underlying data presented in Appendices 7 and 8, as well as the datasets inferred to be the source material, which do not indicate such occurrences near the AMOR. Upon closer examination and georeferencing of Figure 2, it becomes evident that the authors have inadvertently incorporated data from the Schulz Bank. This data might originate from doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.949920, but neither this nor related sources are explicitly cited in the HI Report.

The mentioned Pangaea data and related scientific publications (e.g., Meyer et al., 2023) demonstrate that Schulz Bank hosts rich benthic communities. Despite being one of the best-documented locations for benthic life forms, the HI Report does not designate this area as a priority for 100% protection. This approach of not prioritizing areas with known biological richness and instead focusing on indirect geological proxies is puzzling.

Georeferenced Figure 2 overlying bathymetry and known locations of interest.

GENERAL COMMENTS

HI Report Motivation

In the preface of the HI Report is stated that the *work presented in this report was commissioned to the Institute of Marine Research, Norway by the Norwegian Environment Agency in response to increased human activities in the Nordic Seas.*

Specific objectives of the Norwegian Environment Agency were to identify relevant factors for the evaluation of protection needs through addressing the following questions:

- 1) is it more important to protect rare species and habitats or to protect functionally important ecosystems and**
- 2) do some species or habitats need greater protection than others?**

[Comment](#)

The two questions raised are indeed fundamental to the subject matter. However, a careful review reveals that the HI Report does not adequately address or conclusively answer these critical inquiries, particularly the first one.

Frontpage of the PDF version of the report.

CWC & Sponge Data Outside Study Area – Comment

All data considered in the HI Report is confined to the study area. It is intriguing to analyze how the data behaves outside this restricted zone, particularly the primary biological data utilized in the report, such as sponge aggregations and cold-water coral data, which cluster along the eastern border of the study area.

By removing the study area filter, we obtain the two figures on the right, which clearly show that the majority of data points lie outside the designated study area. The HI Report, commissioned by the Norwegian Environment Agency, focuses specifically on the deep sea (*Denne rapport er en leveranse til bestillingen «rapport om behovet for vern eller beskyttelse av særegne og sjeldne naturverdier i dyphavet» fra Miljødirektoratet til Havforskningsinstituttet*).

However, it raises questions about the value of MPA network recommendations when habitats are arbitrarily divided and most available biological data exists outside the study area. Furthermore, these external habitats are experiencing significant human pressure and are not well protected (see following slides). An integrated approach that considers the entire area and all available data while adhering to established frameworks for systematic conservation planning would be more effective.

Sponge aggregation (left) and cold-water coral data (right) equivalent to HI Report Appendix 7 & 8 but without the study area restriction filter applied.

Human Pressure and Impact on Seabed – Comment

The areas characterized by rich sponge aggregations and cold-water corals largely overlap with regions experiencing the highest fishing intensity, as indicated by the density of Vessel Monitoring System (VMS) records. These areas also show the most trawl marks on the seafloor and the highest concentration of seabed litter.

Figure 1 from Buhl-Mortensen & Buhl-Mortensen (2018).
Overview of indicators of human pressure (A) and impact (B,C) on the seabed.
(A) Annual mean density of VMS records (pings) based on aggregated data for the period 2009–2015.
(B) Number of trawlmarks observed during visual inspections part of the MAREANO mapping programme.
(C) Density of seabed litter observed during visual inspections (MAREANO).

MPAs OSPAR / Norway – Comment

The map reproduced from the [OSPAR Assessments Website](#) on the right illustrates the MPA network within the OSPAR regions as of October 2021. Below, the statistics for individual OSPAR member countries are presented. Norway is significantly lagging behind countries like the UK, which are nearing protection targets.

Figure 1.3: MPA coverage in the national waters of Contracting Parties, comprising territorial waters and EEZ as well as MPA coverage in territorial waters and EEZ separately (as of 1 October 2021).
 Source: Report and assessment of the status of the OSPAR network of Marine Protected Areas in 2021.

Figure 1.1. OSPAR Network of MPAs (as of 1 October 2021)
 Source: Report and assessment of the status of the OSPAR network of Marine Protected Areas in 2021.

MPAs OSPAR / Norway – Comment cont.

A more detailed map of existing and planned marine protected areas as of April 2021 can be found on regjeringen.no (right).

On the same page a map of mapped coral reefs and coral reefs protected against fisheries activity can be found (left).

An additional concern regarding Norwegian marine protected areas is the apparent lack of strict enforcement. This issue has been highlighted, for example, in a [report by NRK](#).

Biological Data vs. Geological Proxy – Comment

In Section 2 of the HI Report the following is stated: *All publicly available scientific data were collected for the area of interest. This comprised biogeographic regions and provinces, geomorphic features and marine landscapes (e.g., canyons, ridges, seamounts, hydrothermal vents) and biogenic habitats (e.g., abundance and diversity of cold-water coral communities and sponge aggregations). The description, definitions and sources of all the layers and data used in this study are given in Appendix.*

As previously mentioned, the sources for some data layers lack clarity, and greater transparency and/or access to the data would enhance the report's value. Claiming that all available scientific data were collected for the area of interest may be overstating the situation. Our analysis indicates that some public data from sources like OBIS are either not utilized or not cited properly.

The HI Report predominantly relies on MAREANO data, which would be fine if supplemented with other scientific data. For instance, the University of Bergen's Centre for Deep Sea Research (established in 2021), which builds on the former Centre for Geobiology (2007–2017) and K. G. Jebsen Centre for Deep Sea Research (2017–2021), has produced publications that do not appear to be considered in the HI Report.

A challenge in this regard is the lack of exact definitions of e.g., grounds, aggregations, etc., which make integration of different datasets difficult.

The biogenic habitats considered in the HI Report are essentially 1) CWC and sponge LDAAs, 2) CWC and sponge HDAAs, and 3) the red listed *Sclerolinum contortum*.

This is in stark contrast to the 30 non-biogenic habitat features categorized as geomorphic features, biogeographic zones, and areas of interest: abyss, slope, arctic biogeographic region (>1000m), Norwegian coast - West Norway, Barents Sea, Southeast Greenland - North Iceland Shelf, High Arctic Maritime, basins, submarine canyons, escarpments, fans, plateaus, ridges, rift valleys, rises, sills, mid-ocean spreading ridges, terraces on the continental slope, troughs, smooth continental slope, marine canyons, deep sea plain, continental slope plain, continental shelf plain, marine mountain landscape, seamounts, knolls, hydrothermal vents, and cold seeps.

Consequently, the MPA models are primarily guided by geological and geographical proxies rather than actual biological data.

REFERENCES

References

The list of references that we directly cite in this presentation are as follows.

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